

A Comparison of Gender Differences and Performance Metrics in a VR-Based Auditory Selective Task

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Abstract— Virtual Reality has gained significant interest with the advancement of display and processing technologies in recent years. Traditionally, visual stimuli were the main point of interest in the development of new VR applications. However, audio is also key to the success of such experiences. Audio technology is responsible for making the VR environment more immersive as it is directly correlated with how we perceive the world. Our real-world environments are multimodal and multisensory. In this work, we investigate the effect of two types of distractors in an auditory selective attention task. Users were immersed in a virtual classroom with spatialised audio enabled. The task itself was divided into two subtasks. First, participants had to identify different types of auditory and audiovisual stimuli in the scene. Second, they had to focus their attention on a speaker in front of them and identify a keyword from the story each time they heard it. Furthermore, participants were divided into three groups that differ on when the distractor is presented in the second subtask: (a) before, (b) same time, and (c) after the keyword. Findings from this study show that there are significant gender differences for listeners immersed in an environment with competing sounds in recalling a story. Moreover, the time when distractors are presented significantly affected the response time, being inversely proportional to the mean response time.

Keywords— *Quality of Experience, Virtual Reality, Selective Auditory Attention, Cross-modal, Multisensory, Central Auditory Processing Disorders.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Virtual Reality (VR) is a technology used in a variety of settings, ranging from entertainment to healthcare systems [1]. It has gained more focus after the COVID-19 pandemic, with an acceleration of the adoption of this technology. The lines between digital and real worlds are blurring, and there now exists a demand for remote, collaborative and virtual experiences [2]. In this context, visual stimulus is one of the main components of VR applications. For this purpose, software and hardware have rapidly evolved over recent years with the objective of increasing the resolution of displays and improving rendering technologies. A second key element of VR is audio. Auditory stimuli have the power of enabling a more immersive experience, as it provides information about the direction and depth of the sound source. Audio is also

connected with human emotions, enhancing the feeling of suspense or tension [3].

A number of VR applications make use of different types of audio systems to create realistic experiences [3], [4]. Stereo and Spatialised audio are common examples of how sound can be used to provide more cues to the user. In the case of VR systems with spatialised audio, objects and other elements in the virtual environment can provide a high sense of presence. Consequently, the user has a feeling of being physically present in the environment [5]. Another important element of auditory perception is related to how this information is processed and interpreted in the brain. More than simply hearing, we are also able to assign meaning to auditory stimuli, which is a more complex task in terms of mental demand [6]. Moreover, we are constantly surrounded by various types of auditory stimuli (e. g. other people, cars, birds chirping, etc.). Therefore, auditory attention becomes a fundamental step towards the comprehension of an auditory stimulus of interest. This skill plays an important role in an auditory selective attention (ASA) task, where listeners filter out auditory information that is irrelevant whilst focusing on the information of interest [7].

Despite all of the mentioned features, auditory stimuli are not explored as much as visual stimuli in VR. Therefore, it is particularly important to investigate how humans perceive and process sounds in such immersive environments [8]. Moreover, attention is a valuable resource, and understanding how it operates differently based on gender provides insight into how attention can be influenced or disrupted for users of immersive multimedia. In this paper, we apply a Quality of Experience (QoE) framework to compare self-reported and performance metrics of listeners in an auditory attention task. Additionally, we extend our analysis by comparing differences influenced by gender (human factors) and stimuli modality (system factors).

The next section outlines the related work, showing how the VR applications were designed to assess listeners in an ASA task. Following this, a detailed description of the adopted methodology is provided along with analysis and discussion of the collected data. Finally, conclusions are drawn, highlighting the main findings of this work.

II. RELATED WORK

The work of Breuer et al. [7] investigated how listeners perform in an ASA task. The authors aimed at translating an audio-only version to a VR-based version of a paradigm to evaluate ASA. Participants were given two controllers and the task consisted of pressing a button on the controller according to the category of the word they hear. For this purpose, the auditory stimuli were split into two categories: (1) flying animals (bee, duck, owl, dove) and (2) non-flying animals (snake, rat, seal, cat). Participants were also presented with auditory distractors positioned at different locations from the target. Their findings show that a VR setting can enhance attention as differences in error rates and response time have been found comparing the audio-only versus VR. Although findings from this work provide evidence of VR as a tool to recreate close to real-life experience, this approach did not adequately address the representation of distractors in the scene. Both target and distractor stimuli in the task were purely auditory, creating a mismatch between participants' vision and hearing. As a result, the auditory reproduction does not encourage participants to rotate their heads, which enhances auditory perception [9]. This effect was observed in their analysis of head movement, where authors reported a low range of head movement. Therefore, further investigation on the impact of distractors and how they are presented in an ASA task is still to be conducted.

A second relevant element when conducting ASA tasks is related to the collected metrics. As outlined previously, the human vision system is strongly correlated with auditory attention [10]. Therefore, the analysis of gaze data and head movement plays a major role in works that explore ASA. In [11], the authors aimed at understanding visual attention in VR for a classroom scenario by analysing their gaze data. In total, 381 participants took part an experiment that evaluated 3 design factors: (1) sitting position of participants (e.g. either at the front or back of the room); (2) level of realism of avatars (e.g. cartoon-like versus realistic avatars); and (3) percentage of hand-rising of virtual peer-learners after the virtual lecturer asks a question. One of the main contributions from [11] is related to how to design a virtual environment that optimises user attention. Authors reported that characteristics of the virtual environment such as graphics quality affect one's visual attention. In their findings, the group that experienced less realistic graphics (cartoons), had a higher time spent on objects whereas the other group spent more time looking at the lecturer and the lecture content. Finally, it showed that gaze data plays an important role in an auditory attention task, with the potential of being used to analyse other components, such as gender differences in attention and how distractors can affect attention.

The review of the works in the literature demonstrates that the integration between 3D sound and virtual or augmented environments enhances the sense of presence and immersion once it enables the listener to be more aware of the surroundings [11]. This validates the usage of VR systems for the assessment of conditions that affect human auditory processing disorder abilities. Works presented in this review provided a guideline for the design of the VR environment in terms of the amount of visual information in the scene, and

Fig. 1: Virtual Classroom showing the position of possible distractors.

nature of distractors [12], [13]. However, factors that influence user QoE (human, system, and context) of multimedia applications were not deeply explored. Considering the related work, the novelty of this work lies in the development of a VR application to assess listeners in an ASA task. We aim at answering the following research question:

“Does gender impact reaction time to target stimulus in an auditory selective attention task in VR that has auditory and audio-visual distractors?”

Our approach allows for the investigation of reaction time as a performance metric to compare (i) gender differences, (ii) nature of stimuli, (iii) time when distractors are presented in relation to the target information.

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Virtual Environment

The virtual environment was designed using the Unity game engine (version 2020.3.19f1) [14]. Some of the virtual objects (e.g. desks, blackboard, chairs, etc.) were sourced using online tools [15] and others were modelled using Blender (version 3.4.1) [16]. The immersive HMD used was the HTC VIVE with Tobii Pro eye-tracking integrated [17]. This headset has a dual AMOLED screen with a field of view of 110°, a refresh rate of 90Hz and a resolution of 1,440 x 1,600 pixels per eye. The system was designed to run wirelessly to allow the listener to naturally interact (look around) with the virtual environment, with 6 degrees of freedom (DoF), and search for the correct sound source. The audio was reproduced by a Beyerdynamic DT 990 PRO Studio Headphones [18], with diffuse-field equalisation. Fig. 1 shows the VR environment designed for this experiment. It simulates a learning environment (classroom) where participants must focus on the speaker in front of them while ignoring other distractors in the scene. The speaker's position is fixed throughout the experiment and lip and facial expressions were added to the avatar using the SALSA LipSync plugin [19]. Animations for other students in the scene and speaker were added using Mixamo [15].

B. Experimental Protocol

Before the experiment began, participants were introduced to the research and signed a consent form. The next stage consisted in checking visual and hearing abilities by performing a colour blindness test and hearing test [20], [21].

TABLE I. STIMULI DESCRIPTION.

Stimulus	Position	Description	Category
Car	Left	Car passing outside	Auditory
Pen	Right	Object falling on the floor	Audiovisual
Control	N/A	Absence of distractor	N/A
Phone	Left	Phone vibrating on the desk	Audiovisual
Footsteps	Right	Footsteps from a person walking outside the room	Auditory

Following this, participants were given an E4 [22] wristband to collect physiological metrics and the VR headset. Following this, headset adjustments and eye calibration were performed to ensure that the content was displayed correctly. Participants remained in the virtual environment for 5 minutes to collect their baseline physiological data. During this stage, they were able to see an empty virtual classroom without the speaker or other students. After baseline data is collected, they were given the controller and started the tutorial. All instructions were presented on the classroom's blackboard in front of them. They were free to move to the next instruction and start the task whenever they felt comfortable doing so.

The objective of both tasks was to identify either distractors or a keyword by pressing a button on the controller. This ASA task was divided into two subtasks. Each subtask presented a different story, sourced from LibriVox [23], a free public domain platform. The presentation order of the parts was randomised. The subtasks for the experiment were:

- *Identification of a keyword (KEYWORDS)*: listeners have to identify a keyword in the talker's speech. The task consisted in pressing the trigger button in the controller whenever participants hear the word "home". In total, this word is repeated 15 times in the story and the story has a length of 3 minutes and 53 seconds. Each keyword is paired with one type of distractor (refer to Table I).
- *Identification of distractors (DISTRACTORS)*: listeners have to identify distractors in the scene. Participants were instructed to press the trigger button in the controller whenever they hear any type of distractor or sounds other than the speaker. The length of this story was 2 minutes and 27 seconds.

Following completion of the two subtasks, participants removed the headset and completed a questionnaire about their experience. Questionnaires measured elements of presence [24], task load [25], and other questions related to the auditory task. The average duration of the experiment per participant was 43 minutes.

C. Target and Distractors

The virtual room is also composed of other elements that might cause disruption and here are classified as distractors. There are two modalities of distractors: auditory and audiovisual. Furthermore, control stimuli were included to represent events that have no distractors. Visual stimuli were

TABLE II: DEMOGRAPHICS OF THE PARTICIPANTS IN THIS STUDY.

Group	Test Order	Sex	Count
-1500	Background Noise	Female	5
		Male	6
	Keywords	Female	6
		Male	7
0	Background Noise	Female	7
		Male	7
	Keywords	Female	6
		Male	6
1500	Background Noise	Female	7
		Male	8
	Keywords	Female	6
		Male	6

not considered for this study as the main objective of this study was the evaluation of auditory attention. A list of distractors and their respective classification is shown in Table I. It is important to note that all distractors are either positioned to the left or right of participants (refer to Table I).

The location of the target stimulus (speaker) is the same for the entire duration of the experiment. This strategy was adopted to ensure that participants would not have to refocus their auditory attention. Therefore, any changes in their attention would be exclusively caused by the presence of distractors in the scene. The order of presentation for distractors was randomised. Each distractor on Table I has a duration of 3s and is repeated 3 times (15 in total which is the same number of times the keyword is repeated).

D. Participants and Group Division

This experiment follows previous studies with similar paradigms on QoE evaluation [26] and auditory selective attention [7]. In total, 79 participants took part in this experiment (age: 19-62 years, $M = 29$ years, $SD = 8$ years, 38 females). Table II represents the demographics of the recruited participants. Inclusion criteria were to be fluent in English and have normal hearing abilities. Two participants were removed from this analysis as they are diagnosed with attention disorders. From this population, 23 participants had never experienced VR before. One of the objectives of this study was to investigate the relationship between the time when distractors are presented impact on the listener. Therefore, participants were randomly assigned into three groups that differ on the time distractor is presented for the KEYWORDS task:

- I. *Before keyword (-1500)*: distractors are presented 1500ms before the target stimulus (keyword).
- II. *Same time as keyword (0)*: distractors are presented together with keywords.
- III. *After keyword (1500)*: distractors are presented 1500ms after the target stimulus (keyword).

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

An Analyses of Variance (ANOVA) was conducted to investigate the main effects of the experimental groups, nature of stimuli and reaction times. Significant values with respect to statistical analysis are presented below with a 95%

TABLE III: MEAN OPINION SCORES (MOS) OF SELF-REPORTED METRICS COMPARING RESPONSES BY GENDER.

	Male		Female		H-value	p-value
	MOS	SD	MOS	SD		
Q1 - "How aware were you of the real world surrounding while navigating in the virtual world"	3.73	2.038	4.24	1.801	1.05	0.305
Q2 - "How much did your experience in the virtual environment seem consistent with your real world"	4.08	1.403	4.00	1.509	0.01	0.913
Q3 - "How real did the virtual world seem to you"	2.93	1.700	2.92	1.605	0.00	1.000
Q4 - "I am able to remember the noise story"	1.68	1.845	3.27	2.050	11.23	<0.01
Q5 - "I am able to remember the keyword story "	4.45	1.782	5.24	1.065	4.95	0.026
Q6 - "I did not feel present in the virtual space"	4.38	1.720	3.76	1.949	2.32	0.128
Q7 - "I felt like I was just perceiving pictures"	1.95	1.600	1.84	1.724	0.20	0.655
Q8 - "I felt present in the virtual space"	5.20	0.853	4.86	1.032	2.69	0.101
Q9 - "I had a sense of acting in the virtual space"	4.68	1.385	4.03	1.323	6.19	0.013
Q10 - "I still paid attention to the real environment"	2.38	2.084	1.89	1.760	0.77	0.380
Q11 - "I was completely captivated by the virtual world"	4.40	1.215	4.57	1.237	0.47	0.495
Q12 - "I was not aware of my real environment"	3.45	2.183	4.03	1.833	1.03	0.309
Q13 - "In the computer generated world I had a sense of being there"	4.65	1.292	4.62	1.114	0.35	0.556
Q14 - "It was not difficult to identify the keyword"	5.30	1.137	4.78	1.512	4.05	0.044
Q15 - "Somehow I felt that the virtual world surrounded me"	4.98	1.097	4.68	1.226	1.19	0.275
Q16 - "The objects in the room distracted me"	4.65	1.833	4.32	2.148	0.49	0.485
Q17 - "The virtual world seemed more realistic"	1.13	1.305	1.62	1.656	1.71	0.190

level of confidence. The experimental group for each subtask was a between-subjects variable while the nature of stimuli and gender were within-subjects variables. Differences between groups for self-reported metrics were analysed using the Kruskal-Wallis test for non-parametric data.

A. Performance Metrics

The first analysis in Table IV is based on the differences between groups in terms of the amount of time in milliseconds participants took to detect (reaction time) the target stimulus for either the KEYWORDS task or the DISTRACTORS task. These differences were analysed separately as each task had a distinct objective.

For the KEYWORDS task, the aim was to measure if the time when distractors were presented had an impact on reaction time in detecting the keyword after it is presented. Results from the ANOVA test on the reaction time yielded significant variation among groups ($F(2, 1051) = 981.75, p < 0.001$). A post hoc Tukey test showed that all groups differed significantly from each other at $p < 0.05$.

TABLE IV: ANOVA RESULTS FOR THE REACTION TIME.

Source of variation	Reaction Time		
	df	F-value	p-value
Between-subjects Effects			
Distractors – Group	2	2.821	0.060
Keywords – Group	2	981.754	<0.001
Within-subjects Effects			
Keywords – Stimuli	2	0.291	0.747
Keywords – Gender	1	0.038	0.844
Distractors – Stimuli	1	15.96	<0.001
Distractors – Gender	1	1.703	0.192

We expected that reaction times for the -1500 and 0 groups would be similar whilst the +1500 group would perform better in comparison with other groups. We hypothesised that the similarities between groups -1500 and 0 would derive from the presence of competing noise in both conditions.

Fig. 2 presents the mean reaction time obtained across stimuli modalities and subtasks. The DISTRACTORS subtask is represented with dotted lines whereas the KEYWORDS subtask is represented with solid lines. Additionally, each colour represents the mean reaction time for one of the stimuli modalities. As predicted, the 1500 group achieved the lowest reaction time. However, the expected behaviour of groups -1500 and 0 was different. Our findings show that reaction time increased when listeners perceived a distractor right before the target information. This disadvantaged condition caused a delay in processing the auditory information, yielding a higher mean response time. Another observation that can be made by analysing Fig. 2 is the relationship between the nature of distractors and reaction time. No statistically significant results were found when comparing these two metrics and the graph shows that they were constant when analysing each group separately.

KEYWORDS subtask is represented with solid lines. Additionally, each colour represents the mean reaction time for one of the stimuli modalities. As predicted, the 1500 group achieved the lowest reaction time. However, the expected behaviour of groups -1500 and 0 was different. Our findings show that reaction time increased when listeners perceived a distractor right before the target information. This disadvantaged condition caused a delay in processing the auditory information, yielding a higher mean response time. Another observation that can be made by analysing Fig. 2 is

Fig. 2: Mean reaction time across stimuli modalities and subtasks.

the relationship between the nature of distractors and reaction time. No statistically significant results were found when comparing these two metrics and the graph shows that they were constant when analysing each group separately.

Regarding the DISTRACTORS subtask, the aim was to investigate differences between reaction time in detecting the auditory or audio-visual stimuli across groups. ANOVA results on this metric did not yield statistically significant differences across groups. As per Table IV, this metric had little variation across groups. However, when comparing the effect of stimuli modality (auditory versus audio-visual) on reaction time, the ANOVA test results show significant differences ($F(2, 1739) = 15.96, p < 0.001$). This can be observed in Fig. 2, where there is a clear separation between reaction times for auditory stimuli against audio-visual stimuli. Additionally, this graph shows that auditory stimuli were easier to identify than audio-visual stimuli.

These results provide an interesting insight into the usage of multimodal stimuli in VR environments. When analysing the DISTRACTORS task individually, it is possible to observe that the mean reaction time varies with the nature of the stimuli. However, this only applies if they are part of the main task, i.e. a situation where the user must focus on perceiving these stimuli. On the other hand, as observed in the KEYWORDS task, when they are not part of the target information and act as distractors, the differences between the modality of the stimuli were not as substantial.

B. Self-Reported Metrics

The questionnaires used in this study are available at [27]. The questions aimed to measure levels of immersion and auditory attention. We first performed a between-group analysis on self-reported metrics, which yielded no statistically significant differences in any of the questions. However, participants from all groups reported a high level of immersion during the task when observing the results for questions Q6, Q7, Q8, and Q13, which aim at measuring levels of presence and immersion.

Interestingly, when comparing results considering gender a number of noteworthy findings emerge. TABLE III presents the results of the Mean Opinion Scores (MOS) for a gender comparison obtained with the post-test questionnaires along with the results from the Kruskal Wallis test. Regarding the questions associated with levels of immersion and presence, Q9 ("I had a sense of acting in the virtual space") was the

Fig. 3: MOS for questions Q4 and Q5 directly related with the auditory selective attentions task.

only one to yield significant differences for gender comparison ($H = 6.19, p = 0.013$). The other questions that resulted in p values less than 0.05 are all related to how participants felt about their own performance in each subtask. Q14 ("It was not Difficult to Identify the keyword") shows statistically significant differences ($H = 4.05, p = 0.044$) in this comparison with a greater median value for males. Q4 refers to the question: "I am able to remember the distractors story" whilst Q5 refers to "I am able to remember the keywords story". Both Q4 and Q5 are related to remembering the theme of the story at the end of the experiment. Participants were asked to write down keywords that best describe each story in order to validate their answers. Results from the Kruskal-Wallis test indicate that the population median was different across gender [Q4: ($H = 11.23, p < 0.01$), Q5: ($H = 4.95, p = 0.026$)]. For Q4, 55% of females reported remembering the DISTRACTORS story at some extent ($MOS \geq 3$) against 24% from males. For Q5, 94% of females reported remembering the KEYWORDS story against 80% from males following the same criteria. This finding is particularly interesting for Q4, which evaluates the DISTRACTORS subtask. We expected that all participants, independent of gender, would have difficulty in remembering the story, given that the objective of the task is to pay attention to stimuli other than the speaker telling the story. However, females were able to better remember the details of both stories. This can be observed in Fig. 3, where females obtained a MOS of 3.27 and 5.24 for Q4 and Q5, respectively. In contrast, males obtained a MOS of 1.68 and 4.45 for Q4 and Q5, respectively. Overall, both males and females were able to remember the details of the story presented in the KEYWORDS, subtask. Such findings were expected as in this part of the experiment participants have to actively drive their attention to the speaker. Although females reported remembering the distractors task story more than males, no statistically significant differences in performance were found when analysing reaction times in each subtask. The results of this comparison are presented in Table IV. A p-value of $p = 0.84$ was obtained for the KEYWORDS subtask whilst a p-value of $p = 0.192$ was obtained for the DISTRACTORS subtask, which is closer to being statistically significant.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This work presented a VR system designed to assess the user in an auditory selective attention task. The experimental design was inspired by the state-of-the-art QoE frameworks that use both self-reported and objective metrics. We aimed at measuring levels of immersion and presence along with other questions related to the auditory attention task and participants' reaction time. Findings from this work show that reaction time increases when a distractor is presented before or at the same time as the stimulus of interest. Furthermore, the initial research question related to the impact of the nature of the stimuli over reaction time was answered. In the task where the objective was to identify auditory and audio-visual stimuli, the type of stimuli had an impact on reaction time, with lower values for audio-visual stimuli. However, this is no longer the case when these stimuli act as distractors, and we did not find significant evidence to support this statement. Finally, we reported that females achieved a better score when attempting to remember the theme of a story whilst there is competing noise in the background. Future work will explore other objective metrics commonly used in QoE frameworks to investigate if gender differences can be correlated with other performance metrics such as reaction time and number of correct responses.

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